

Immunoglobulin A vasculitis in an adult patient receiving vedolizumab therapy for ulcerative colitis: A Case report

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ABSTRACT Immunoglobulin A-associated vasculitis (IgAV), is an inflammatory disease characterized by the deposition of immunoglobulin A1 in the small vessels of the skin, joints, kidneys, and gastrointestinal tract. Here, the author describes the case of a 28-year-old woman undergoing vedolizumab treatment for ulcerative colitis who presented with a palpable purpuric rash followed by classic symptoms of IgAV.

KEYWORDS IBD, ulcerative colitis, IgAV, vedolizumab, vasculitis, purpura

Introduction

Immunoglobulin A-associated vasculitis (IgAV); known previously as Henoch-Schönlein purpura is a small vessel vasculitis, characterized by deposition of Immunoglobulin A1 complex in the small vessels of the skin, joints, kidneys, and gastrointestinal tract. It typically presents with palpable purpuric rash, arthralgias, gastrointestinal and renal manifestations [1,2].

IgAV is traditionally considered to be a childhood disease, but new emerging evidence suggests its incidence is increasing in adults. Hočevár et al. reported the highest annual rate of 5.1 cases per 100,000 adults (95% CI: 3.4 - 7.4) [3]. The exact aetiology of adult IgAV is still unclear, and various underlying factors have been proposed, including infections, vaccinations, medications, and malignancies [4,5,6].

Case report

A 28-year-old woman diagnosed with ulcerative colitis for two years that was effectively managed with 5-aminosalicylates. Upon disease progression, confirmed by colonoscopy, the patient was prescribed vedolizumab. This antibody-based treatment enabled her to achieve remission with no adverse effects.

Two days after her fourth vedolizumab dose, the patient presented with multiple non-blanchable, palpable purpura on both legs (figure 1). The patient had experienced similar skin lesions prior to initiating vedolizumab treatment that resolved without treatment. However, in this episode, the lesions were more extensive and persistent. Her vital signs were within healthy limits. Urine analysis detected hematuria but no proteinuria. Basic laboratory tests were performed including a white blood cell (WBC) count ($8 \times 10^9/L$), platelet count ($320 \times 10^9/L$), hemoglobin (12 g/dl), creatinine (57 mmol/L), urea (3.4 mmol/L), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR; 28 mm/h), c-reactive protein (CRP; 43 mg/L), serum IgA (3.74; healthy range: 0.65-4.21), C3 (1.26), and C4 (0.22). Other serum rheumatological markers of small vessels vasculitis were negative. A skin punch biopsy analyzed by light microscopy showed leukocytoclastic vasculitis with considerable perivascular neutrophilic infiltration. Direct immunofluorescence (DIF) revealed superficial dermal vessels positive for IgA, consistent with IgAV pathology.

For eight weeks, the patient had multiple emergency department visits for worsening skin lesions that expanded to involve both her upper and lower limbs, associated with newly migratory polyarthritides with effusion and severe epigastric abdominal pain with vomiting. The patient was admitted with concerning laboratory test results including an elevated WBC count of $21 \times 10^9/L$ (mostly neutrophil), platelet count of $618 \times 10^9/L$, ESR at 49 mm/h, and CRP of 30.7 mg/L. The patient was prescribed prednisolone (1 mg/kg/day) along with omeprazole (40 mg/day). Subsequently, the abdominal and joint pain improved but not the skin lesions. Dapsone (1 mg/kg/day) was started to combat the prednisolone-resistant skin lesions but

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Figure 1: Non-blanching palpable purpura on lower extremity.

was withdrawn after two weeks due to the development of methemoglobinemia and drug-induced cholestasis. Abdominal computed tomography (CT) appeared normal. The patient was discharged on slow reducing dose of oral prednisolone. At the 2-week clinical follow-up, the patient's symptoms had improved considerably, and her lab results were all within the normal range.

Discussion

Vedolizumab is a humanized monoclonal antibody approved in 2014 for the treatment of moderate to severe inflammatory bowel disease. It targets integrin $\alpha 4\beta 7$, an adhesion molecule unique to gastrointestinal tract blood vessels, and inhibits leukocyte adhesion and, thereby, prevents inflammation. It has a good safety profile and carries few side effects [7].

There is one reported case of IgAV developing in a patient with Crohn disease treated with vedolizumab [8]. Other reports of cutaneous lesions in patient receiving vedolizumab include the exacerbations of nodular vasculitis [9] and worsening pyoderma gangrenosum [10]. Regarding the case described here, since similar skin lesions preceded the vedolizumab treatment, it's unlikely to be vedolizumab induced vasculitis but, rather, the manifestation of another underlying inflammatory condition that worsened in the presence of vedolizumab.

Without high clinical suspicion, IgAV in adults is challenging to diagnose. There are two criteria used to confirm IgAV: The 1990 American College of Rheumatology (ACR) criteria [11], and the more recent 2010 EULAR/PRES/PRINTO criteria [12]. The ACR requirements for IgAV diagnosis include the presence of at least two of four designated symptoms (age at onset \leq 20 years old, palpable purpura, acute abdominal pain, biopsy

with granulocytes in the walls of small arterioles or venules); this results in diagnostic sensitivity and specificity of 87%. According to the EULAR/PRES/PRINTO, IgAV is defined as the presence of purpura or petechiae (mandatory criterion) with a lower limb predominance not related to thrombocytopenia plus one of the following: (1) abdominal pain; (2) arthritis or arthralgia; (3) renal involvement; and (4) histopathology with DIF evidence of IgA reactivity. Employing this criterion yields a sensitivity of 100% and specificity of 87%. The patient described in this case study met the criteria for IgAV according to both diagnostic criteria.

In general, the patient prognosis depends largely on renal involvement. For adults, the risk of developing long-term renal complications is higher than for the pediatric population [13,14]. Early recognition and management of such complications are warranted, using serial urinalysis to detect hematuria or proteinuria in the first six months after diagnosis [15]. For severe recurrent skin lesions that don't respond to steroid treatment, dapsone seems to be effective. However, the associated side effects (e.g., methemoglobinemia, hypersensitivity syndrome, and the rapid recurrence of skin lesions upon cessation [16]) often preclude its use. In our patient, both methemoglobinemia and drug-induced cholestasis led to the discontinuation of dapsone.

Treatment strategies for IgAV remain controversial. However, IgAV that presents without renal involvement is thought to be self-limiting [17]. 94% of children and 89% of adults recover fully within four weeks of onset [18]. For the patient described here, the lengthier disease course could be partly explained by the exacerbating effects of vedolizumab and its long elimination half-life (25.5 days) [19].

Conflict of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest to declare by any of the author of this study.

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